

Research Article

Collaborative Development of Obesity Intervention Strategies and Digital Tools in Denmark

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Received 19 September 2025; Revised 4 November 2025; Accepted 4 December 2025

Academic Editor: Qing-Wei Chen

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This study examines the results of the application of a bottom-up approach for collaboratively developing effective strategies and digital solutions for obesity prevention and healthy behavior promotion in Denmark. The results of two rounds of participatory workshop sessions conducted in early 2024 involving different stakeholders and target users are described. The results of the study confirm that bottom-up approaches, coupled with technological innovation, constitute an effective instrument to address the socially context-dependent and complex nature of obesity. The codeveloped intervention strategies and digital tools offer evidence-based suggestions for policymakers, health practitioners, and developers who want to invest in sustainable, user-initiated approaches to preventing obesity.

Keywords: bottom-up approach; design thinking; digital tools; intervention strategies; obesity; user-centered design

1. Introduction

Obesity prevalence in Denmark has risen markedly over the past decades. Whereas in 1987 only 6.1% of adults were obese (BMI \geq 30), in 2021 this figure was 18.4%, a tripling [1]. This rise has included all ages and is overall driven by broad societal, lifestyle and environmental changes. Without any significant interventions, these rates are anticipated to increase to 34% among males and 24% among females in Denmark by the early 2040s [2].

Public attitudes to the etiology of obesity are also shifting. In a survey in 2023, Danes mainly attributed unhealthy diet, lack of exercise, structural conditions, social and psychological aspects, and hereditary factors as causes of obesity [3]. All these findings refer to the need for complex solutions that go beyond top-down policy or one-size-fits-all interventions. To address the issue effectively, combined and personalized efforts (e.g., policy intervention, education, and community-based support) will be required.

Top-down conventional reductions in obesity have limited success as a stand-alone driver of change. Some public health programs risk being professionally driven and insufficiently adapted to the everyday realities, challenges, and aspirations of the populations they are intended to serve [4]. Bottom-up approaches, including participatory methods and user-centered design (UCD), have been successful in informing public health obesity-prevention interventions and codesigning digital solutions that are user-friendly, accessible, and sustainable [5]. These approaches enable the involvement of different stakeholders in cocreating services and products, as well as codeveloping technological tools [6–9]. By enabling the involvement of everyone, the approach ensures that the resulting solutions are better aligned with user needs and context congruent. The evidence illustrates that participatory methods can enhance user engagement, satisfaction, and retention in healthcare interventions, particularly when cocreation methods are used in the design of digital tools for lifestyle change [10].

Moreover, UCD methods applied to digital health interventions, such as mobile apps or web-based programs, have been shown to successfully improve adoption and adherence through fitting the technology to users' daily lives and personal interests [11, 12].

Building on these considerations, this paper aims to explore the advantages of adopting a bottom-up approach in the development of effective obesity intervention strategies and in cocreating usable digital tools. The research question guiding this study is the following:

How can multistakeholder engagement assist the collaborative development of more effective intervention strategies and digital tools for obesity prevention?

To answer this question, the results of two rounds of participatory workshop sessions conducted in Denmark in early 2024 are described. In the workshops, various stakeholders were involved (e.g., end users, educators, health professionals, and sports organizations) to collaborate on designing intervention strategies and functionalities of digital tools to drive long-term healthy behavior change.

These workshops have been part of the HealthyW8 project, funded by the European Commission in 2023 and conceived to address such complexity with the amalgamation of participatory, multidisciplinary, and technology-driven methodology for the prevention of obesity.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 1 introduces the background and research question. Section 2 introduced some literature works applying bottom-up approaches for obesity prevention in Denmark, while Section 3 describes the methodological approach adopted in the participatory workshops. Section 4 presents the results from the two rounds of workshops. Section 5 discusses the findings. Finally, Section 6 provides conclusions and outlines directions for future research.

2. Related Work

As obesity rates continue to rise, there is growing recognition that traditional top-down interventions often fall short in addressing the complex and context-specific factors driving the obesity disease. In response, Denmark has increasingly turned to bottom-up approaches.

A relevant example of an effective bottom-up approach is the Generation Healthy Kids project, which demonstrates how large-scale planning can be guided by such an approach. This national project engaged a wide range of stakeholders (e.g., government agencies, NGOs, teachers, and community leaders) in a group model-building exercise to identify the structural drivers of childhood overweight and obesity in Denmark [13]. Participatory system mapping facilitated the identification of gaps within interventions and supported the design of context-relevant solutions tailored to Danish communities. It empowered local actors and enhanced intersectoral collaboration, illustrating the potential of bottom-up strategies to drive systemic changes.

The Sundhed og Lokalsamfund (SoL) Project [14] exemplifies how a bottom-up approach can successfully promote healthier lifestyles among Danish children aged 3–8 years and their families. Conducted in several Danish

municipalities, the SoL project engaged municipal staff, citizens, and local shop owners in codesigning healthy eating interventions (e.g., store reorganization, in-store campaigns, and public festivals). The participatory nature of the SoL project not only provided greater local stakeholder buy-in and compliance but also facilitated longer-term behavioral changes compared to top-down mandated interventions.

Also, Denmark's use of human-centered design in obesity prevention is exemplified by several initiatives, most notably the development of a weight-neutral health intervention, which the University of Copenhagen has been endeavoring to advance [15]. This codesign initiative involves individuals living with obesity, clinicians, and researchers in ongoing participatory workshop. The aim is to integrate lived experiences and professional insights into the intervention design and the development of intervention components encompassing the physical and psychosocial aspects of obesity, promoting self-acceptance, supporting intuitive eating, reducing weight stigma, drawing on user experience and user needs, and granting access to non-stigmatizing health communication materials for healthcare providers [15]. The bottom-up nature of the process ensures not only clinical relevance but also cultural appropriateness and user-friendliness. Besides, the MOVE application was created and pilot-tested using human-centered design approaches to encourage physical activity and social integration among Danish citizens physically challenged due to various health conditions. Incremental testing of the application, from pilot testing to user workshops, was used to reach accessibility as well as cultural relevance [16]. Similarly, a Danish partnership project targeting childhood obesity employed a mixed-methods approach, including stakeholder workshops, focus groups, and interviews to codesign and prototype an app aimed at supporting family-based lifestyle changes. The initiative included iterative testing and parental involvement for optimal real-world usability and effectiveness [17].

The present study illustrates the application of a bottom-up approach in the collaborative development of intervention strategies and digital tools for obesity prevention. It draws on participatory workshop activities in Denmark in early 2024 as part of the HealthyW8 project. The data gathered through these workshops contributes to the design of appropriate and effective solutions to prevent obesity.

3. Materials and Methods

The research design used for the participatory workshops adopts a bottom-up approach. Specifically, it blends UCD with design thinking (DT) [11, 18, 19] as described in D'Ulizia et al. [20].

Two rounds of workshops were set up to gather user requirements and experiences regarding intervention strategies and the definition of technological tools for healthy lifestyles and to discuss, identify, and prioritize intervention strategies and desired tool functionalities of the HealthyW8 solution portfolio.

The participants were selected through an outreach program engaging parents of primary school children,

young adults, older adults, healthcare professionals, representatives from sports organizations, educators, members of the academic/scientific communities, and other citizens. The study recruitment period was from October 1st, 2023, to February 1st, 2024. Selection was based on voluntary participation, with priority given to individuals who had direct experience with the topic or professional involvement in the fields of nutrition, physical activity, education, or public health. During the recruitment process, efforts were made to ensure gender balance and to include participants with varied lived experiences and needs to enrich the discussions.

The primary objectives of the first round were to collect user requirements to determine which features should be incorporated into the HealthyW8 portfolio and to actively engage key stakeholders to better understand their needs, motivations, and experiences regarding the intervention strategies that should be employed to encourage healthy lifestyles. Therefore, the “understanding” phase of UCD and the “empathize” and “define” phases of DT were utilized.

The second round encompassed the “ideate” and “prototype” stages of DT, as well as the conceptualization stage of UCD. In addition to generating ideas for desired functionalities deemed crucial and beneficial for the design and development of the HealthyW8 tool (HLRS: Healthy Lifestyle Recommender System), this activity aimed to involve participants in the discussion, identification, and prioritization of intervention techniques.

The second round completed the ideation and prototyping phases of DT and the conceptualization phase of UCD. This activity sought to engage participants in discussing, identifying, and prioritizing intervention strategies, as well as generating ideas for desired functionalities considered significant and beneficial for the design and development of the HealthyW8 tool portfolio.

A testing phase will be built into the short pilots starting in August 2025 to verify the optimal intervention strategies and tool features identified in the earlier phases.

In Figure 1, the methodological approach followed within the participatory workshops is shown.

Please note that the present study primarily focuses on the outcomes of the two rounds of participatory workshops; the results of the testing phase are beyond the scope of this work.

The results of the two rounds of participatory workshops conducted in Denmark in January-February 2024 are presented in the following sections.

4. Results of the Analysis

Four workshops were organized overall with forty-four participants. The first round comprised 24 participants (13 in the cocreation workshop and 11 in the codesign workshop), while the second round comprised 20 participants (11 in the cocreation workshop and 9 in the codesign workshop). To facilitate active participation and in-depth exchange of ideas, participants in the first-round workshops were divided into three smaller discussion groups of 3–5 individuals. In the second-round workshops, participants were divided into two groups of 4–6 individuals. Group

composition was mixed in terms of representatives of each stakeholder category (e.g., young adults [18–25 years old], older adults, citizens, parents of primary schoolchildren, healthcare professionals, educators, representatives from sports organizations, and academics) to promote cross-sectoral dialogue and to capture contrasting yet complementary perspectives.

The outcomes of the first and second round workshops will be discussed separately in the following paragraphs, thereby enhancing the qualitative analysis.

4.1. Evidence From the First Round of Workshops. Two participatory workshops were conducted during the first round on January 29th, 2024, one for the cocreation of intervention strategies and the other for the codesign of technological tools. Participants in the first workshop included two parents of primary school children, one young adult, one healthcare professional, three representatives from sports organizations, one educator, three members of the academic/scientific community, and two other citizens. The second workshop included two parents of primary school children, one young adult, one healthcare professional, two representatives from sports organizations, three members of the academic/scientific community, and two other citizens.

4.1.1. Intervention Strategies Emerged From the First Cocreation Workshop. The workshop on the cocreation of intervention strategies aimed to gather needs, motivations, and experiences regarding the intervention tactics that should be employed to encourage healthy lifestyles. To guide the discussions, three key questions were posed to the various stakeholders. Participants were invited to reflect on and describe the following topics:

- Personal experiences related to eating habits and behaviors that support a healthy lifestyle
- Challenges encountered in adopting such habits and behaviors
- Perceived needs required to overcome these challenges and facilitate a healthy lifestyle.

In relation to the first point, several participants indicated that they generally thrive to maintain a healthy lifestyle but face various barriers. These challenges were particularly evident among young adults, who, due to living in dormitories or away from home for educational purposes, often struggle to sustain healthy dietary and lifestyle practices. Other participants reported attempting to follow healthy diets but not always succeeding due to personal taste preferences or medical conditions. While some participants demonstrated a theoretical understanding of what constitutes a healthy diet, including knowledge of recommended and discouraged foods, this knowledge alone was insufficient to ensure consistent adherence to a healthy eating behavior. Conversely, healthcare professionals noted that emotional factors significantly influence eating habits, observing that individuals have limited practical knowledge and experience

FIGURE 1: The methodological approach followed within the participatory workshops. *Source:* Provided by the authors.

with healthy eating. Instead, they often opt for convenience foods, such as prepackaged meals, take-away options, meal boxes, and ‘pop-diets’ (popular among both children and adults). Physical inactivity was also identified as a common issue. Additionally, participants noted that many people eat while watching television or using mobile devices and frequently purchase food online, where they are exposed to conflicting health messages. Finally, time is rarely devoted to preparing healthy food, as the priority is often on work, career obligations, and social engagements.

The positive influence of parents on their children’s eating habits was widely acknowledged; in fact, parents take care to prepare healthy meals, discuss nutrition and health with their children, involve them in cooking activities, and include them in grocery shopping. Furthermore, they emphasized the importance of promoting healthy lifestyles within schools, for example, by preparing nutritious lunch boxes and advocating for cooking lessons as part of the curriculum.

Despite these positive aspects, educators report that many pupils exhibit a problematic relationship with food, particularly girls who seem highly concerned about body image and fear of weight gain and therefore engage in excessive physical activity and food avoidance. This behavior appears to be driven largely by social media influences, leading to unrealistic body ideals and social isolation of those who are overweight.

This perspective is shared by sports organizations, according to which many individuals are overly focused on their physical appearance, exercising excessively, and neglecting proper nutrition. One participant remarked that ‘sport dictates when food is consumed’, highlighting the imbalance between physical activity and dietary habits. Nevertheless, members of these organizations show considerable mutual support and care within their communities.

Finally, the broader scientific community emphasized the importance of establishing healthy lifestyle habits early in life, noting that behaviors formed during childhood often persist into adulthood. They stressed the need to raise awareness among young people about making informed food choices and advocated for the joint involvement of families and school environments in fostering food literacy, which can lead to healthy eating habits. Additionally,

academics expressed concern about the low adherence to expert dietary advice, with many individuals, especially youth, preferring guidance from influencers or other public figures who often lack nutritional expertise.

Regarding the second discussion point about barriers to adapting healthy eating habits and behaviors, participants identified several key barriers. These included a general lack of nutritional knowledge and the absence of clear policies, particularly in relation to educational materials targeted at younger populations. Furthermore, healthy alternatives and meals were perceived as costly and time-consuming to prepare. Some citizens also reported dietary restrictions related to specific health conditions.

From the parents’ perspective, sedentary life was frequently mentioned as an obstacle, primarily due to peer influence. Educators reinforced this concern, noting that ‘school canteens often serve unhealthy meals’ and that children have insufficient opportunities for physical activity during the school day.

Focusing specifically on families, healthcare professionals emphasized that difficulties tend to arise in families where a natural and relaxed relationship with food has not been established, often due to limited early exposure to nutritional knowledge. Sports organizations added that many parents lack awareness of the appropriate nutrition for children engaged in sports activities. Within such environments, numerous social events feature unhealthy food and beverages such as pizza, beer, and fast food.

Finally, the scientific community identified several additional barriers that individuals face in adopting and maintaining a healthy lifestyle. These include limited opportunities for physical activity in daily life, boredom, misinformation spread via social media, pressure from others, social environment, aggressive marketing by the food industry, and the convenience and accessibility of fast food.

Regarding the identification of needs to overcome the abovementioned barriers, the most pertinent needs identified were (i) reducing the cost of nutritious food to improve accessibility, (ii) increasing public awareness and education about coeliac disease and other diet-related health conditions, (iii) promoting regular physical activity through infrastructure improvements, such as the development of more cycle paths in various countries, and (iv) implementing

stricter regulations on the food industry, particularly regarding the marketing of confectionery and other unhealthy food products.

Participants also emphasized the need for stronger collaboration between families and schools in delivering nutrition education, particularly targeting children. Both parents and healthcare professionals advocated for implementing nutrition education into the school curriculum in a way that is interactive and engaging, to facilitate the adoption of healthy lifestyle behavior.

Additional needs included a greater choice of healthier food options in school canteens and allocating more time for physical activity and education during the school day. Lastly, participants underscored the importance of a supportive and nurturing environment and activities that promote mental and, consequently, physical well-being.

Participants were then divided into three groups and asked to discuss the following topics:

- Existing intervention strategies identified in the literature as most effective in promoting a healthy lifestyle
- Additional intervention strategies they are aware of
- Suggestions for improving existing intervention strategies to enhance effectiveness and applicability.

Table 1 lists the current intervention options that were analyzed during the group discussion on the first discussion point.

Participants were asked to vote for the intervention strategies in Table 1 they consider the most relevant.

The number of votes assigned to each intervention strategy is shown in Figure 2 (only the strategies that received at least one vote are shown). The highest-voted strategies included “Promoting nutrition standards in early care and education settings, food pantries, and faith-based organizations” and “Supporting children and families who are at higher risk for obesity through services at Qualified Health Centers”.

In addition to the predefined intervention strategies, participants proposed several new approaches during the second discussion point, particularly emphasizing institutional support and the active involvement of young people. Some of them included enhancing the personal experience of participation and engaging companies in the health promotion efforts. Socially, participants recommended stricter regulation of social media platforms and influencers to ensure the dissemination of accurate health information and to encourage positive behavioral change. Environmentally, suggestions included establishing tobacco-free sports grounds and soda-free school campuses. At the institutional level, participants advocated for increased awareness and education within public institutions and implementation of differential taxation of food items to incentivize healthier food choices.

Regarding the third area of discussion, there were some intervention strategies proposed to make existing interventions more effective towards promoting healthier lifestyles. These proposals lay stress upon the use of technology, the promotion of collaboration, and enhanced

education to create an all-encompassing framework for promoting healthier lifestyles. Technological innovations were seen as particularly promising for increasing engagement. Examples included gamified programs, like *Pokémon GO*, which encourage physical exercise through walking in urban environments, and active gaming consoles like the Wii, which integrate movement into play for children. In addition, learning devices (e.g., youth-oriented recipe books and calorie visualization software) were also suggested as effective means of raising nutritional awareness.

Strengthening community engagement through collaboration among municipalities, institutions, and organizations was identified as a crucial component of effective intervention strategies. In particular, municipalities were encouraged to support initiatives that promote outdoor physical activities and invest in sports facilities tailored to different age groups.

Additional solutions focused on fostering healthy habits from an early age, such as encouraging children to participate in the preparation of nutritious meals and implementing interdisciplinary health education from early childhood through secondary school. Within educational settings, participants suggested offering free nutritious meals and limiting screen time to encourage physical and social activities.

Lastly, participants were also invited to vote on the two most pertinent cutting-edge intervention strategies that emerged during the preceding discussions, highlighting those considered most impactful for combating obesity and promoting healthier lifestyles.

As shown in Table 2, the intervention strategies receiving the highest number of votes included enhancing cooperation among organizations (e.g., sports clubs, schools, and municipalities), which received seven votes, and the provision of free nutritious food in institutions, which focused on the economic aspect and received six votes.

Other highly appreciated strategies included the use of gamified applications (e.g., *Pokémon GO*), aimed at promoting physical activity and healthy habits across different population groups (five votes), and dissemination of interdisciplinary health education across all institutions to raise awareness (four votes). Other strategies that gained attention included the creation of a cookbook for young people transitioning to independent living (two votes) and increased investment in leisure activities and calorie visualization tools to support physical activity, each receiving one vote.

4.1.2. Functionality Requirements of the Tool Identified in the First Codesign Workshop. During the first codesign workshop, participants were invited to share their experiences and expectations regarding digital tools for promoting healthy lifestyle behaviors and discuss user requirements to identify the functionalities that should be configured in the digital tools (HLRS) of the HealthyW8 portfolio. Participants were asked to describe:

- Their experiences using digital tools (e.g., mobile apps, web platforms, and recommender systems) that

TABLE 1: Existing intervention strategies analyzed during the group discussion.

Intervention strategies

Area (1) Strategies at political/governance level:

1. Studying what works in communities to make it easier for people to be more physically active and have a healthier diet.
2. Measuring trends in obesity and related risk factors.
3. Developing and promoting guidelines on dietary patterns and amount of physical activity people need for good health.
4. Helping families with lower incomes access affordable, nutritious foods.
5. Supporting children and families who are at higher risk for obesity through services at Qualified Health Centers.
6. Funding programs and providing training and resources for initiatives that promote healthy eating, food and nutrition security, and physical activity.

Area (2) Strategies at social level:

1. Making it easier to choose healthy food options where people live, work, learn, and play.
2. Making healthy foods more available by connecting local producers with retailers and organizations such as childcare, schools, hospitals, and food hubs.
3. Promoting nutrition standards in early care and education settings, food pantries, and faith-based organizations.
4. Partnering with business and civic leaders to plan and carry out local, culturally tailored interventions to address poor nutrition, physical inactivity, and tobacco use.
5. Designing communities that connect sidewalks, bicycle routes, and public transportation with homes, early care and education settings, schools, parks, and workplaces.

Area (3) Strategies at healthcare level:

1. Measure patients' weight, height, and body mass index, and counsel them on keeping a healthy weight and its role in disease prevention.
2. Screen children and adults for overweight and obesity and refer patients with obesity to intensive programs, including family healthy weight programs and the Diabetes Prevention Program.
3. Counsel patients about nutrition, physical activity, and optimal sleep.
4. Use respectful and nonstigmatizing, person-first language with all individuals in weight-related discussions.
5. Connect patients and families with community services to help them have easier access to healthy food and ways to be active.
6. Discuss the use of medications and other treatments for excess weight.
7. Seek out continuing medical education on the latest on obesity science.

Area (4) Strategies at individual level:

1. Eat a healthy diet by following Dietary Guidelines.
2. Get the amount of physical activity recommended by professionals.
3. Get enough sleep.
4. Manage stress.
5. Talk to their healthcare providers about available obesity prevention and treatment options to help reduce potential health risks.

FIGURE 2: Selection of the intervention strategies by participants and the corresponding number of votes received.

TABLE 2: New intervention strategies suggested during the group discussion with their corresponding votes.

Suggested intervention strategies	Received votes
A cook-book for young people moving away from home.	2
Cooperation between organizations (e.g., sports), schools, and municipalities.	7
Municipalities should support this.	
Disseminate healthy interdisciplinary measures across all institutions (from crèche and up).	4
Free food in institutions.	6
Invest more money in leisure activities to make people move more: increased facilities.	1
Use gamification to target different groups to get more exercise, e.g., Pokémon GO, city walks including storytelling, Wii.	5
Visualization of the association between calories in different foods/meals (e.g., a cake) and how much physical activity you need to perform to “burn” these calories (walk, run).	1

support healthy lifestyle behaviors such as physical activity, healthy dietary habits, and weight management.

- Challenges encountered when using these digital tools to maintain a healthy lifestyle.
- Perceived benefits of using these digital tools to support healthy lifestyle behavior.

Regarding the first point, all participants reported knowing and using various apps that track calorie intake, step counts, and fitness routines. Younger users, in particular, frequently used social media platforms to access workout programs and advice on nutrition and sports.

Regarding the use and perceived benefits of digital tools for supporting healthy lifestyle behaviors, participants shared a range of experiences across different stakeholder groups. Sports organizations reported using platforms, such as *Holdsport* and *Teamsport* (available as both apps and web interfaces), which provide comprehensive access to nutritional advice, activity plans, and schedules. One participant also mentioned audiobooks as a motivational tool for encouraging walking in public spaces.

Parents of primary school children highlighted the utility of the *Holdsport* app in structuring and scheduling training sessions, as well as facilitating communication between children, parents, and coaches. For older children, *Swimify Live* was mentioned as a useful platform for accessing live coverage of swim competitions.

Healthcare professionals had an even broader knowledge of mobile applications, including *Lifesum* and *Madlog* for carbohydrate tracking (particularly for individuals with type 1 diabetes), *Dankost* for dietary registration, and *MyFitness* for exercise monitoring. They also frequently consulted official Danish nutrition websites for evidence-based guidance¹.

Members² of the scientific community acknowledged the value of existing digital tools: dietary and exercise tracking apps (e.g., *Lifesum*), informational platforms (e.g., *Aula*, a Danish school site), and intervention-oriented apps (e.g., *Pokémon GO*, *Geocaching*, and *Wikiloc*). They also expressed interest in more experimental tools, including the ‘Are you

too sweet?’ tool, which monitors children’s sugar intake relative to recommended levels, and applications to track movements and sleep quality.

Participants identified several challenges associated with the use of digital tools for promoting healthy lifestyle. Common issues included inaccurate or incomplete information, lack of regular updates, and barriers related to language or socio-economic status. Users also reported difficulties in coordinating between multiple apps or feeling overwhelmed by the amount of available information. Additionally, some tools featured influencers whose body images were perceived as unrealistic and potentially contributing to negative self-perception.

The scientific community provided more insight, noting that registration apps alone do not directly lead to behavioral change. Moreover, intervention apps have the inherent problem of promoting greater use of devices, even though screen time can be harmful. Furthermore, these apps “take time away from togetherness”, and some users face technological barriers such as resistance to digital tools or compatibility issues across devices and app versions.

Recommendations for improvements focused on integrating validated content and incorporating features that enhance user engagement, such as gamification and peer support. Participants suggested that reminders for physical activity and app usage should be linked to tools that track the impact of physical activity on emotional well-being. Additionally, the design of these tools should be intuitive, user-friendly, and accessible to individuals who are not regular users of digital health technologies. Academics stressed the importance of initial motivation, recommending that apps be relevant, helpful, and designed to encourage real-life activities. They also advocated for integration with social media platforms and the use of appealing graphic design to enhance user experience.

In conclusion, it was noted that only one individual (a scientist) reported having no experience using digital tools to support a healthy lifestyle. The reason given was a lack of motivation to use such apps, although their usefulness for others was recognized. This individual did not believe personal interest could be increased but imagined that others

could be incentivized by apps that count calories and steps or offer measurements on everyday activities.

The next step in the codesign process involved creating user personas and reviewing app mock-ups to ensure the tools address the diverse needs of different user groups. While there was interest in digital tools for promoting healthy lifestyles, challenges related to accuracy, accessibility, and professional guidance remain.

Afterwards, participants were shown videos illustrating the functionalities of existing digital tools previously developed by the partners in the HealthyW8 project, such as Gamebus² [21] and Nutrida³. They were then invited to discuss in three groups and propose ideas regarding:

- Which existing digital tools most effectively promote a healthy lifestyle
- Which functionalities of existing digital tools shown in the videos best support behavior change toward healthier lifestyles
- New functionalities that could be implemented to further promote a healthy lifestyle.

Regarding the first discussion point, all groups indicated Gamebus due to its diverse features (i.e., sports, sharing, and gamification). It was described as more intuitive, fast and handy, full of features. However, its extensive range of functions may make it feel unfocused and untargeted.

Whereas the second group agreed with the first statement, participants added that none of the digital tools shown in the videos could effectively encourage a healthy lifestyle, as they were considered too complex to use.

Regarding the functionality of current digital tools, respondents focused on aspects related to exercise and menu planning. They mentioned the importance of being able to select focus areas and choose between different types of physical activity.

Moreover, they explored the functionality to create a personalized diet plan, where many decisions are made by the tool, requiring users to simply follow the meal recommendation. Furthermore, they appreciated the community components that enhance sharing and a sense of togetherness, although group competitions could potentially have negative effects on those who do not win.

For the third discussion point, one suggested functionality to be incorporated into existing digital tools was the integration of the Nutrida app with additional functions, such as visual comparisons between the amount of food consumed (e.g., using images) and the corresponding calories that should be burned.

The third group suggested the possibility of connecting with other apps, while the second group proposed integrating existing apps and elements into a single platform. These approaches would centralize and calibrate information and functionalities to suit individual needs. The user should be placed at the center of what is referred to as a ‘holistic approach’, in which health encompasses physical, mental, social, and other aspects. To be effective, digital tools should consider physical activity, family logistics, sleep, screen use, mood, grocery shopping planning, skills, and

diets. Additionally, digital tools should be free to use, ensuring accessibility for all, with a strong focus on user-friendliness.

Another significant suggested improvement was linking the app to practical, real-life activities, thereby supporting a sense of community that extends beyond the digital realm and enhances users’ sense of belonging. Examples of such activities could be physical (or virtual) meetings, celebrating events, or cooperation with local sports organizations, restaurants, and religious communities.

Finally, participants were asked to vote on the two most relevant functionalities that emerged from the previous discussion, as reported in Table 3.

Table 3 details the proposed functionalities for new digital tools aimed at enhancing user engagement and promoting healthy habits. According to voting results, the most endorsed feature (receiving six votes) was “Gamebus: meeting physically (or virtually) and celebrating events, including eating together. Cooperation with local sport organizations, restaurants, and religious communities”. Other noteworthy suggestions included the “Holistic approach” and “Integrating existing apps and elements in one platform”, each receiving five votes. The former emphasizes the integration of mental, physical, and social well-being to develop an app that supports all these dimensions, while the latter advocates for a centralized tool that incorporates everything necessary to facilitate a healthy lifestyle.

The proposal “apps free to use and accessible to all” received moderate support, with three votes. The last proposal, which received one vote, was the possibility to connect with other apps; this low level of support is likely due to the similarity of this suggestion to the idea of integrating everything into a single app.

4.2. Evidence From the Second Round of Workshops. Two additional participatory workshops (the third and fourth) were conducted during the second round on February 7th, 2024, one on the cocreation of intervention strategies and the other on the codesign of technological tools. Participants in the third workshop included one parent of a primary school student, one young adult, one older person, one educator, one healthcare professional, two representatives from sports organizations, two members of the academic/scientific community, and two citizens. The fourth workshop included three parents of primary school students, one young adult, one older adult, one educator, one member of the academic/scientific community, and two other citizens.

4.2.1. Intervention Strategies Ideated During the Second Cocreation Workshop. The second workshop on the cocreation of intervention strategies consisted of two main stages: (1) a critical assessment of the two most voted intervention strategies and (2) the design and prototyping of those strategies.

In the first phase, participants critically examined a range of intervention strategies across three macroareas: (a) developing technological tools/reward programs to promote a healthy lifestyle, (b) promoting educational and training

TABLE 3: Suggested functionalities of new tools from the group discussion, with their corresponding votes.

Suggested new tools' functionalities	Received votes
Gamebus: meeting physically (or virtually) and celebrating events, including eating together. Cooperation with local sports organizations, restaurants, and religious communities.	6
Holistic approach where health includes physical, mental, social, etc. health. The group made a drawing with a circle including movement (e.g., Garmin activity tracker), family logistics (especially a calendar function), sleep, screen use (work, school, leisure time), mood, grocery shopping planning, community peer-to-peer (many kinds, for example, buddy arrangements), skills (e.g., in sport: I want to learn to...), diet.	5
Integrating existing apps and elements in one platform.	5
Possibility to connect with other apps.	1
The app needs to be free to use if it should be accessible to all.	3

programs for healthy living, and (c) implementing tools/initiatives to disseminate trustworthy information on a healthy lifestyles and obesity prevention (see Table 4). It should be noted that the intervention strategies explored in this phase received the highest number of votes both in the first round of the Danish workshop (see Table 2) and in workshops held in other countries participating in the project.

For each macroarea, participants identified both advantages and disadvantages as detailed below. In macroarea A, strategies like apps promoting physical activity (i.e., sports apps) and those related to calorie tracking were perceived as very useful because people enjoy monitoring and sharing their progress with others. Sharing progress and creating communities is also possible through platforms and gamification features. Economic incentives such as cashback were seen as having long-term benefits, especially when combined with personalized tools. Automated recommendations were perceived as sustainable, although they may be too generic to effectively meet individual needs.

Several disadvantages were identified within macroarea A. Sports apps, information platforms, and age-tailored programs were considered unattractive to individuals who do not already have healthy habits. Furthermore, these tools may contribute to social pressure and, when combined with gamification, increase screen time, potentially reducing real-life social interaction. Finally, economic incentives, such as cashback and corporate bonuses for students/workers, might be difficult to implement and potentially not very inclusive.

In macroarea B, educational activities targeting parents at the school level were appreciated for their potential to promote healthy lifestyles and cultural changes but faced challenges related to long-term adherence and effectiveness, alongside the risk of exclusion, particularly in programs aimed at children. Emotional education programs targeting stress and low self-esteem were recognized as beneficial but challenging to implement across diverse individuals because they require a personalized approach. Finally, refresher courses for practitioners were seen as valuable for increasing knowledge and awareness of the topic. These should be incorporated into training programs but risk being ineffective if not supported by practical intervention strategies.

In macroarea C, trustworthy information dissemination strategies, such as verified apps and national platforms, were seen as reliable, free, and accessible but raised concerns about the volume of information, which might be too similar to existing tools. Participants suggested that information and clarification campaigns, sports events, and the involvement of influencers could make the topic more interesting, especially for younger people, ensuring inclusion. At the same time, these initiatives could be perceived as less credible or authentic and may not reach those who need them most.

Finally, the dissemination of 'healthy lifestyle' interdisciplinary measures across all institutions, making the health topic an integral part of the educational process, may also be useful, but to achieve this, schools would need to reorganize their schedules.

In the second phase, participants focused on the two strategies that received the most votes (5): emotional education services to better manage emotional states (macroarea B/strategy d) and disseminating 'healthy lifestyle' interdisciplinary measures across all institutions by including them in school schedules (macroarea C/strategy e). They were specifically asked to discuss and make suggestions for:

- Key stakeholders that should be involved in putting the intervention strategies into practice.
- Technological tool(s) that can facilitate the implementation of the intervention strategies.
- Approaches to tailor the intervention strategies to the characteristics of the users.

Regarding key stakeholders (point a), health professionals such as doctors, psychologists, school nurses, and dieticians were essential for interventions to guide healthy lifestyles. To support emotional education, primary caretakers, teachers, pedagogues, the Ministry of Education, and developers of tools and education materials were also suggested (strategy B-d). To ensure the dissemination of new knowledge about the topic (strategy C-e), they recommended including municipalities, spokespersons for organizations (e.g., heart or sports associations), and nutrition experts.

Regarding technological tools (point b), participants suggested integrating multimedia like videos with experts (i.e., meditation for strategy B-d), as well as screening tools

TABLE 4: Most voted intervention strategies identified during the first round of local workshops.

<p><i>Macroarea A: To develop technological tools/reward programs for promoting a healthy lifestyle</i></p> <p>a. Apps that promote physical activities</p> <p>b. Cashback and/or corporate bonuses for students/workers who are engaged in physical activity or adopt a healthy lifestyle (e.g., biking to work).</p> <p>c. Information platform for medical information, calories calculation, and groups of common interests</p> <p>d. Automated recommendation systems based on science and taking into account the specifics of the region (promoting healthy local food)</p> <p>e. Tailoring tools/programs according to the individual and his/her age</p> <p>f. Use gamification to engage different population groups in physical activity, e.g., Pokémon GO, city walks including storytelling and Wii.</p>
<p><i>Macroarea B: To promote educational and training programs for promoting a healthy lifestyle</i></p> <p>a. Educational activities targeting parents at the school level (daycares, preschools, etc.) and nudging them to improve eating habits at home</p> <p>b. Cartoons (using kids' language) explaining what obesity is and its consequences</p> <p>c. Educational programs at school, kindergarten</p> <p>d. Emotional education services conducted by trained professionals and targeting school and work environments to help individuals better manage emotional states such as low self-esteem, stress, and guilt</p> <p>e. Systematic refresher courses for healthcare professionals</p> <p>f. Regular seminars and campaigns on "distress" as a major factor for obesity</p>
<p><i>Macroarea C: To implement tools/initiatives for disseminating trustworthy information on a healthy lifestyle and obesity prevention</i></p> <p>a. A verified app endorsed by accredited authorities with a virtual operator to answer questions</p> <p>b. A national platform (made available by the Ministry of Health), where people can find detailed and trustful information on various health aspects; one of them could be obesity</p> <p>c. Information and clarification campaigns, sporting events, etc. at the national, regional, or even company level</p> <p>d. Initiatives for eliminating stereotypes and create new references on healthy lifestyles (e.g., by promoting influencers beyond social networks who participate in community networks and offer quality information on healthy eating and lifestyles)</p> <p>e. Disseminate 'healthy lifestyle' interdisciplinary measures across all institutions by including them in daily life/school schedules for all children in all institutions (e.g., it could be exercise, knowledge about diet, food, nutrients, physical activity, mental health, etc.)</p>

that let students answer sensitive questions anonymously. In general, the use of mobile devices and computers could be useful for online consultations both with professionals and others facing similar challenges. However, caution is needed with the use of chatbots that lack emotional depth and may misdiagnose mental issues. On the other hand, many automated technological functions can be used by healthcare professionals to encourage a healthy lifestyle, including daily reminders to promote new healthy habits. For disseminating 'healthy lifestyle' interdisciplinary measures, they proposed creating apps that allow schools and health professionals to collaborate. This could include an education portal with exercises and information. Suggested tools included interactive boards, AR/VR, and 3D printing with fast login and response times.

In terms of tailoring the intervention strategies, the personalization of strategy B-d was considered essential by all participants (except for the screening tool, which should be standardized). They recommended adapting strategy based on characteristics like culture, gender, and children's ages. Daily observations of behavior/lifestyle using scales (e.g., stress levels) and individual responses were proposed to monitor single situations and provide suitable suggestions. For strategy C-e, opinions were mixed. Most participants believed that personalizing the information would be too challenging and therefore preferred a general dissemination approach tailored to different age groups. Others believed personalization could be helpful but recognized that this would require educators with the right competencies.

4.2.2. Tool Functionalities Ideated From the Second Codesign Workshop. The second codesign workshop consisted of two main stages: (1) the design of user personas and (2) the design of the most voted functionalities of the digital tools.

Personas [22, 23] are invented characters that represent different types of end-users who might use the HealthyW8 toolkit. Participants were shown draft descriptions of personas for both primary end users (such as children, young adults, and older adults) and secondary stakeholders (such as educators, caregivers, and health professionals). This helped ensure the digital tools would meet the needs of various user groups and to gain a better understanding of the key target users and stakeholders who would use and benefit from the tools. Figure 3 illustrates an example of a primary user persona.

Personas were refined through group discussion to capture specific demographic and behavioral characteristics to provide personalized services. This information included family background and personal history. The digital tools should clearly specify specific aspects of physical well-being, including height-to-weight ratio and levels of physical activity. To further personalize recommendations, the individual's eating habits, as well as those of close relatives, should be made more explicit. These tools should investigate eating habits and preferences to facilitate the generation of a customized shopping cart. Furthermore, the importance of the user's social context was highlighted, as well as information about friends and colleagues. The work context was also relevant; specifying the occupation (including that

Persona Child: Cecilie

Type of user: Child (Primary)
Country: Denmark
Age: 13 years
Family status: Lives with mother, father and little brother (9 years)
Education: 7th grade
Profession: School child
Disabilities: None
Chronic conditions: ADHD, anxiety
Food Intolerance or allergy: None
Leisure time interests: Gymnastics twice a week
Food habits and preferences: Not picky, interested in a varied diet, likes to bake, helps with cooking at home, has a cooking day every Tuesday. Favorite dishes: lasagna, salmon, fruit. Likes snacks.

Goals

- Cecilie would like to look like Taylor Swift.
- Become more confident when she experiences new “things”.
- Get rid of her anxiety.
- Become more independent.
-

Cecilie often uses her mobile phone. She is often on SoMe. Her mother has undiagnosed ADHD, and Cecilie would like to become more independent from her parents and be more away from home on her own. Gymnastics is more a social thing with her girlfriends. She had difficulties concentrating before her diagnosis, but after it has become much easier. It has also become easier to get friend because she resembles the other girls more now, and can participate in conversations. She does not interrupt them as much after receiving her ADHD medicine. Cecilie is normal weight and has a normal height. Her parents work from 8-16, and the entire family has normal weight and height. However, the father is a little shorter than the average.

FIGURE 3: Example of a user persona developed during the codesign workshop. *Source:* Provided by the Danish partners of the HealthyW8 consortium.

of family members), along with work shifts and working hours, would help in understanding how meals can be best managed. Finally, participants also proposed changing the way ‘personas’ are written, because they appear to focus on problems and what the individual is failing to do, rather than motivations and personal strengths.

To allow participants to contribute to the development of the “perfect” tool, the functionality of existing digital tools was demonstrated, i.e., Nutrida, GameBus, and Experienter. The participants, divided into the same two groups, developed the following concepts. The first group imagined a tool capable of adapting to the end-user’s needs. Upon login, a dashboard would appear with access to various other apps covering different dimensions including sleep, diet, physical activity (similar to Endomondo), mood, social relations, screen time, and medication. For example, a sleep quality app (see Figure 4) would monitor sleep and offer advice on improving dietary habits, such as reducing caffeine intake. A nutrition app, inspired by Nutrida, would include an innovative feature linking nutritional information to affordability using tips on local shop deals. Further, an app

that targets the social aspect would aim at reducing loneliness and building relationships, and offers support by highlighting community events, tailored to the user’s age. The second group proposed an app designed to inspire and support users in their daily lives. Such an app would be accessible via smartwatches and smartphones and integrated with other apps (e.g., *Pokémon GO* and *Lifesum*) and would include features such as Face ID. As far as personalization is concerned, specific user groups would be targeted, namely children (i.e., gamification rewards and parental control of the apps) and individuals over 65 (i.e., features to monitor menopause), addressing individual needs. Key features would be reminders and motivational messages to encourage progress. Another concept involves monitoring bowel health using the Bristol Stool Scale, with daily tracking. For nutrition, the app would use AI to scan photos of meals and calculate calories intake. It would also offer personalized dietary recommendations, such as supplementing the diet with missing vitamins or flagging potential health concerns. These suggestions would be delivered via pop-ups based on user input, allowing targeted guidance.

Example on how the sleep app could look like:

FIGURE 4: Example of an app created by Danish workshop participants. Source: Provided by the Danish partners of the HealthyW8 consortium.

5. Discussion

This paper summarizes the findings from four participatory workshops held in Denmark on January 29th and February 7th, 2024. Each workshop was conducted in two rounds to collect user requirements and experiences related to intervention strategies and the design of technological tools for promoting a healthy lifestyle.

The first workshop of the first round focused on the cocreation of intervention strategies, gathering needs, motivations, and experiences related to intervention tactics that should be used to encourage healthy living. Based on the discussions, participants chose to concentrate on two key strategies: “promoting nutrition standards in early care and education settings, food pantries, and faith-based organizations” and “supporting children and families at higher risk for obesity through services at Qualified Health Centers”. Participants voted for the most promising intervention strategies from their point of view, selecting cooperation between organizations (e.g., sport clubs), schools, and municipalities by majority vote. The main support was

expected from municipalities. Additional suggestions included providing free food in institutions and using gamification to engage different groups in physical activity (e.g., *Pokémon GO*, city walks with storytelling, and Nintendo Wii).

The second workshop of the first round focused on the codesign of technological tools to support healthy lifestyle behaviors. The participants discussed their experiences with digital tools, such as mobile and web apps and recommender systems. The challenges and benefits of using these digital tools to support a healthy lifestyle were discussed. The key recommendation was to integrate existing apps and elements into a single platform that adopts a holistic approach where health is considered in physical, mental, and social dimensions. One example was the “Gamebus” initiative, which allows users to meet in person or virtually and participate in different events. Successful implementation of such tools may require cooperation with local sports organizations, restaurants, and religious communities.

The first workshop of the second round was organized to critically assess, design, and prototype the most voted intervention strategies in the previous sessions. There were three groups of intervention strategies: (1) developing technological tools/reward programs for promoting a healthy lifestyle, (2) developing educational and training programs for promoting a healthy lifestyle, and (3) developing tools/initiatives for disseminating information on healthy lifestyle and obesity prevention. The most voted tool for promoting a healthy lifestyle was “the usage of gamification to engage different population groups in physical activity”. As for the programs, the majority of votes went to the “emotional education services conducted by trained professionals and targeting school and work environments to help individuals better manage emotional states”. Concerning the dissemination tool, the dissemination of ‘healthy lifestyle’ using interdisciplinary measures across all institutions by including them in daily life/school schedules for all children in all institutions received the most votes. Participants also discussed the types of professionals who could potentially be involved in implementing these strategies, the specific features and functionalities of the most voted technological tools, and the opportunities for personalizing the intervention strategies to better meet individual needs.

The second workshop of the second round focused on conceptualizing potential end-users to design detailed “personas” and on refining the functionalities of the most voted digital tools identified in the previous workshops.

Building on the findings obtained from the four participatory workshops, the following section discusses how these findings align with existing evidence in the scientific literature. Specifically, it aims to assess whether the most voted intervention strategies and technological tools identified during the participatory workshops are supported by, and consistent with, prior research on healthy lifestyle promotion and obesity prevention.

Community capacity building strengthens the political power of communities, which, in turn, can be used for the implementation of initiatives that reduce factors leading to

obesity. A growing body of evidence highlights the importance of participatory approaches in contributing to community capacity building. The literature confirms that municipalities play a crucial role in this process [24]. This role involves coordinating efforts across urban planning, education, business, justice, transportation, and environmental services by means of active participation from community representatives, including parents and educators [24].

The readiness of municipalities is an important factor in the successful implementation of capacity-based strategies to prevent obesity. It would be useful to learn more about potential barriers that arise along the way. Schröder et al. [25] analyzed municipal readiness to address childhood obesity prevention in terms of resources, knowledge, attitudes, and culture. The study identified several limiting factors, such as a lack of prioritization and support from leadership and community members, insufficient knowledge and problem awareness, as well as a lack of human and financial resources [25]. Although these findings are based on research conducted in Germany and may not be directly transferable to a Danish context, they provide useful lessons from a neighboring country.

The potential of gamification to increase the effectiveness of childhood obesity prevention interventions is confirmed in the literature [26–28]. Gamification is a recognized and powerful tool for imparting knowledge and improving dietary habits and behavior, allowing people to move towards a healthier lifestyle in a motivating and pleasant environment [28].

Taking into account the multifactorial nature of obesity, a holistic approach to prevention is very promising. Holistic solutions can help weight management services to support and complement each other, thereby increasing the overall efficiency of obesity prevention interventions [29–33].

During this study, many obesity prevention measures were critically assessed and discussed by workshop participants, which likely enhanced the quality and relevance of the most voted decisions. However, not all proposed measures were found feasible. For example, one of the most voted measures during the first workshop was free school meals as implemented in Finland and Sweden, which is undoubtedly a key tool for increasing food literacy and nutrition education in children [34, 35] but was considered politically unfeasible in Denmark.

Consistent with existing literature, this study identified digital technologies in obesity prevention interventions as a measure to increase the effectiveness of such interventions. Evidence from many other studies suggests that utilizing digital technology tailored to different developmental stages can significantly support healthcare providers in addressing the obesity epidemic, particularly when interventions focus on both physical activity and healthy dietary habits [36].

A systematic review [37] explored the use of various digital components and interaction types in counseling interventions aimed at addressing childhood and adolescent obesity. While differences between intervention and control groups were modest, the review found that digital interventions have tremendous potential for the improvement of healthcare

delivery and maximization of resource use. Effective two-way interfaces combining digital and in-person technologies were demonstrated to enhance engagement between youth and adolescents. Moreover, digital interventions offer low-cost alternatives; however, it is of utmost significance that healthcare professionals, particularly nurses, have the skills necessary to effectively employ such tools.

The main strength of our study is its participatory design, which ensured direct involvement of end-users. This approach provided the collection of valuable insights and feedback, helping the development of ideas that can potentially enhance intervention outcomes through improved user adoption, overall engagement, satisfaction, and retention. The great advantage of this method is that most ideas selected during the discussion process were critically assessed, allowing participants to identify potential barriers and eliminating the unrealistic and less feasible measures early in the process. Even though the end-users involved in the workshops were very diverse, some important stakeholders were still missing, such as the Danish Health Authority and the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration. The main barrier to broader stakeholder participation was time constraints. This challenge was addressed by limiting the duration of each workshop and conducting two workshops on the same day, which can also be considered an advantage of the study design in terms of efficiency.

The evidence gathered from four workshops conducted in Denmark in 2024 contributes to the growing body of knowledge needed to plan future obesity prevention interventions and interventions promoting a healthy lifestyle. The most discussed and voted-on intervention strategies and technological tools seem both achievable and promising in terms of their potential effectiveness in obesity prevention. Further participatory studies could expand the background for better understanding and analysis of factors influencing the balance between participant groups to improve the efficiency of such workshops.

6. Conclusion

The results of the Danish participation workshops provide strong evidence that the development of intervention strategies and digital solutions for healthy living may be significantly improved through participatory design processes.

The participants codesigned a range of strategic recommendations, such as free school lunches, gamified exercise tools, and integrated school-based health education, that align closely with current best practices in obesity prevention. Concurrently, participants codesigned functionalities of digital health tools that support a holistic approach to well-being, incorporating features, such as sleep tracking, mood monitoring, social connectivity, meal planning, and physical activity tracking. It is important to note that gamification and event-driven engagement were identified as important motivators for the youth segment.

Through such workshops, participants also critically reflect on the scalability and feasibility of proposed measures. For example, while free school meals were widely supported, participants acknowledged that their

implementation in Denmark might be constrained by political factors. This reflective element of participatory design not only gives preferred solutions more practicality within the content but also enhances stakeholders' ownership and confidence in the process. Effective implementation of the proposed measures requires active involvement from policymakers to create supportive and participatory environments that strengthen community capacity and make health-promoting interventions accessible, appealing, and sustainable for all community members. Specifically, cross-sectoral coordination platforms could be established that engage urban planners, educators, health professionals, and community representatives in joint decision-making to facilitate community capacity building. Besides that, tailored digital tools could be part of municipal health programs, thus enabling practitioners to expand outreach, improve personalization and ensure the sustainability of obesity prevention initiatives.

The study answers the research question positively since it identifies that not only it is possible to develop more effective intervention strategies and digital supports for obesity prevention through bottom-up approaches, but the undertaking in terms of developing user-centered, adaptive, and innovative interventions is also enhanced. Integrating user experience and perspective at the initial stages of the design process allows more personalization, improves compliance, and increases the likelihood of success in health promotion interventions.

Furthermore, the study confirms the overall hypothesis that bottom-up approaches, combined with technological innovation, constitute an effective instrument for addressing the socially context-dependent and complex nature of obesity. The participatory design process enables early identification of enablers and barriers, fosters alignment with users' everyday realities, and facilitates cross-sector collaboration, key ingredients to the success of long-term public health initiatives. Follow-up research needs to upscale this participatory process across diverse national and cultural contexts and explore how consequent digital tools perform under pragmatic implementation conditions. In addition, involving other under-represented stakeholders, such as food regulators and policymakers, could further improve intervention design and delivery. The Danish workshops thus give a glimpse into how participatory strategies can act as agents of change for the campaign against obesity by bringing evidence into action.

Future research should look at the sustainability and long-term impact of the codesigned digital interventions and tools. Comparative studies across countries or cultures could establish the transferability and flexibility of participatory approaches. Finally, longitudinal evaluations of user adoption and health outcomes will be required to validate the effectiveness of these participatory-designed interventions in actual contexts.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Disclosure

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Funding

This research receives funding from the European Commission through the Project HealthyW8 (grant agreement number 101080645) and the European Union under the call HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-01-two-stage and the topic "Prevention of obesity throughout the life course".

Acknowledgments

We thank all stakeholders involved in the workshops and all the members of the HealthyW8 working group: Torsten Bohn, Farhad Vahid, Laurent Malisoux, Yvan Devaux, Manon Gantenbein, Michel Vaillant, Jonathan Turner, Mahesh Desai, Adriana Voicu, Yannick Naudet, Jorge Ribeiro, Alberto Noronha, Adam Selamnia, Serge Autexier, Anke Koenigschulte, Roumen Nikolov, Vladislav Jivkov, Alexandre Chikalanov, Sarah Forberger, Mireia Faucha, Edo Bazzaco, Zein Kallas, Amelia Sarroca, Djamel Rahmani, Maria Giovanna Onorati, Tiziana De Magistris, Elsa Sousa De Lamy, Josep A. Tur, Cristina Bouzas, Giuseppe Tarantino, Michele Stecchi, Ying Wang, Daniela Rodrigues, Yoanna Ivanova, Boyko Doychinov, Pieter Van Gorp, Astrid Kemperman, Pietro Dionisio, George-Mihael Manea, Joost Wesseling, Chrysa Makridi, Cristina Barragan, Ciro Avolio, Marianna Kalliostra, Ezgi Kolay, Katarzyna Janiszewska.

Endnotes

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